

Deep Learning for Disaster Relief: Generating Synthetic High Resolution Images

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

With rapid innovation and technologies, data has become ubiquitous and trillions of bytes of data are generated every second. Deep learning has become phenomenal for processing that immense amount of data and leveraging it for building intelligent models, proving capable of solving various real-world problems. Among the myriad of applications of deep learning, disaster relief is one of the most important. This project, done in collaboration with UNITAR Operational Satellite Applications Programme (UNOSAT), focuses on leveraging deep learning models for generating synthetic high-resolution images focusing on Generative adversarial networks (GANs) to help to generate synthetic images. In particular, this project uses a novel conditional progressive GAN approach and it was trained and validated on the satellite images of the flood in Myanmar provided by UNOSAT.

ABSTRACT

The advancements in engineering and technologies have boosted the unprecedented development in the field of remote sensing. The amount of details modern satellites can capture carries immense value to a wide range of applications. Such high-resolution satellite imageries help us to generate a lot of information about the geography of the earth. Apart from applications in most earth science disciplines; those imageries also have applications in humanitarian works. As a part of the CERN Openlab project in collaboration with the UNITAR Operational Satellite Applications Programme (UNOSAT), this project aims at exploring the possibilities of using conditional progressive growth of GANs, where the conditioning is based on multiple encoders for image generation and image completion. Image completion is a very important problem in processing satellite images because of various reasons. Sometimes, the images taken by satellite under various impeding weather conditions might not be clear and missing parts need to be filled by extrapolation.

In addition, high-resolution satellite imageries are very often licensed in such a way that it can be difficult to share it across UNITAR, UN partners, and academic organizations. This reduces the amount of image data available to train deep learning models. Thus, to overcome this, the possibility of creating spectrally valid images using conditional progressive GANs with multiple encoders is explored in this project.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Satellite imagery has become useful for various research works and humanitarian purposes. They have applications in diverse fields like meteorology, oceanography, geology, intelligence, etc. It is also equally important in defence works. Lately, satellite imagery has been widely used in regional planning, monitoring disasters, and conducting relief works. It provides a base for geographical reference which assists planners and engineers in making plans and executing them. Among a lot of humanitarian works where satellite imageries are used, disaster relief is one of them.

According to the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR), more than 4.5 billion individuals were affected by natural disasters between 1998 and 2017. In the situations where human-induced catastrophic events like war, industrial mishaps, terrorism, and so forth are thought of, the figure is considerably higher [1]. The risks involved with such disasters can however be mitigated if the earlier analysis can be done [2]. The risk analysis of such problems involves understanding the risks we know, figuring out the risks that are not known, and trying to figure out the ways in which probable risks can be tackled. For this, deep learning models have been used extensively. Also, even after such severe catastrophic calamities have occurred, satellite imageries can be of great help to plan and monitor the relief works. Relief works mostly require a high level of coordination with more than one parties and, in such cases, satellite imageries can serve as a very important asset for making plans and managing the flow of the relief works.

The satellite imageries however come with certain limitations. The satellites cannot always take images of the desired sites. The impending conditions such as cloudy environment, constraints laid by trees, or any other objects don't always allow satellites to get the desired images more clearly. For this, various image imputation and extrapolation techniques need to be used. Satellite imageries have a lot of information and even a small obscure spot can be a problem when it comes to the analysis of critical risks. For this, images need to be completed before the critical information is inferred from them.

Another major setback while dealing with satellite imageries is that they are licensed and can be used only by the authorized body. This makes the satellite imageries less accessible and for that reason, not everyone gets to use satellite imageries for the research works they want to carry out. The objective of UNOSAT, a collaborator of CERN with which the project is being done, is to support evidence-based decision making for peace, security, and resilience. UNOSAT has been guiding emergency teams in various disasters like the Ebola pandemic in West Africa, Nepal Earthquake 2015, the Syrian conflict, etc. through maps and satellite imageries [3]. To meet this objective and continue to help even more number of affected areas, the work must involve a large number of stakeholders. One thing that is impending smooth working in such collaboration is that the high-resolution satellite imagery is very often licensed in such a way that it can be difficult to share it across UNITAR, UN partners, academic organizations, and a lot of bodies involved in humanitarian relief works. Since the images are licensed in such a manner, the amount of image data available for research activities is limited. This fact has inhibited research possibilities of UNITAR and collaborating organizations in various ways. Thus, the creation of realistic and images that are spectrally valid can help to mitigate the problems.

For creation of such high-resolution images, the power of computer vision is often used. Computer vision tries to solve various fundamental problems like image extension, recovery of old images, object removal, inpainting of removed parts and so on [2019 Hong]. Deep learning, especially generative models, can be really useful in solving the problems of image completion. In this project, the conditional progressive Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) with multiple encoders is used to solve our problem of image extension. This new approach tries to complete the missing part by taking the known part of the image into consideration. The likely values value for missing part is strictly conditioned on the parts of image that are known. The input is taken as a 256 X 256 image which is further sliced into four tiles of 128 X 128 dimensions each. The objective is to complete the bottom right tile using the information conditioned from the given three slices. The completed image may not be as same as the original image but appears visually realistic and semantically plausible.

2. RELATED WORKS

Image completion problems in general is the most sought-after problem in computer vision. Image inpainting, image outpainting, image completion, etc. are some of the major fundamental problems in computer vision. Prior to the generative adversarial models, basic algorithms like copy-and-paste texture synthesis, geometric partial differential equations (PDEs), coherence among neighbouring pixels, etc. were used for image inpainting [4]. With increasing computational power and unprecedented research in the field of generative adversarial models, the recent research in image inpainting has been widely based on GANs [5-8]. Image outpainting, a problem different than image inpainting, aims to create the unseen surroundings of the image based on given visual content. In this problem as well, GANs seem to work very well [9-11]. Image completion, on the other hand aims to solve both image inpainting and image outpainting (extrapolation).

3. ISSUES WITH PREVIOUS MODELS

The previous models do not use a strict conditional GAN but a combination of multiple techniques. In this implementation, a newer approach is used. The newer approach used is strictly based on GAN and more precisely, the conditional version of the Progressive GAN (ProGAN) [12]. Figure 1 shows the original ProGAN architecture. This approach has helped to get the missing part whose distribution is similar to the original image.

Figure 1 Progressive GAN approach

A DIFFERENT APPROACH

Unlike most previous works using a combination of reconstruction, contextual or/and adversarial losses, this method is strictly conditional and only (Conditional) GAN-based so that it preserves the key-feature of CGAN: the ability to generate samples approximating the full predictive distribution for a new observation. Generative adversarial Networks (GAN) are generative models which produce sample from a distribution approximating the distribution of the data [2014 goodfellow]. Briefly, two neural networks, respectively the Generator (G) and the Discriminator (D), play against/with each other. In the case of image generation, the Discriminator takes as input real images from a dataset and fake images from the Generator. It is a classifier aiming to distinguish real from fake images. The Generator takes as input a noise vector. It aims

to fool the Discriminator. Both networks are trained simultaneously. Eventually, the Generator ends up generating images mimicking the distribution in the dataset.

MULTIPLE ENCODERS

The major issue having a strict GAN architecture lies in the fact that the dimension of the conditional part, which is the known part of the image, is too large to be directly injected as input into the Generator. The known part of the image must be encoded to reduce its dimensionality. The dimension reduction through encoding creates a bottleneck limiting the quantity of information transmitted to the Generator. To tackle this issue, we introduced secondary encoders re-injecting information after the bottleneck through convolutional layers and concatenation. These secondary encoders are simple convolutional and downscaling layers concatenated to the Generator after each deconvolutional block. So, the Generator can learn at each level the most interesting pattern from the input. Figure 2 illustrates the architecture. During the training the Generator is progressively growing. The conditional encoders are added

progressively at the same time as the corresponding block.

Figure 2 Architecture of the CProGAN-ME

Since we want to have the larger bottleneck as possible, we removed the first layers of the original ProGAN's Generator. Instead of starting the training with a 4x4 resolution, we started it with a 32x32 resolution. It reduces conveniently the training time. In the opposite, the transition during which a new progressive block and the corresponding encoder are added during the training requires to be longer because there are more new weights to train. Overall, the training of our conditional progressive GAN based on multiple encoders (CProGAN-ME) is still faster than the original ProGAN and the number of weights in the Generator and the encoders together significantly smaller than in the original Generator.

4. EXPERIMENTS

The experiments were done on flood images, provided by UNOSAT. The CProGAN-ME is trained on the given images and the trained generator is used on the images that is hold out for the validation purpose.

DATA AND PREPROCESSING

For this experiment, satellite images of flood in Myanmar were taken. The dataset was created using Copernicus Sentinel-1 satellite imagery by UNOSAT. The image is S1A_IW_GRDH_1SSV_20160805T114607_20160805T114632_012465_0137A7_ACBC_Orb_TC.tif. From the long name, the several details about the image can be found.

- S1A = image type: Sentinel 1 from ESA Copernicus Hub
- 20160805T114607_20160805T114632 = acquisition time in format YYYYMMDD. The images were captured in August 2016
- ACBC = unique identifier

Figure 3 Sample images (256 X 256) used for training

- Orb_TC = pre-processing done: orbit file (Orb) and Terrain Correction (TC)

The image size is (29184, 21504) which is further sliced into images of size 256 X 256. When the original image is sliced, we get 9,576 smaller images of size 256 X 256. Each 256 X 256 image is further sliced into four tiles of 128 X 128 size. The model is then given three tiles leaving the fourth bottom right tile. The objective is to complete the bottom right tile based on the conditional information from the given three tiles. The dataset is a single channel grayscale dataset. Some of the samples can be shown in figure 3. For the training, 8576 images are taken and for the validation, 1000 images are hold out.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experiments were run on 4 NVIDIA V100 graphics card GPU with 32 vCPU, 256 GB RAM, 4 X 800 GB local cache hard disks and EVS hard disk size of 500 GB. The infrastructure was set up by T-Systems. The infrastructure -a single Virtual Machine (VM)- was provisioned and configured using a tool developed by CERN IT. This tool, written in Python and bash, relies heavily on Terraform. The provisioned VM uses a custom image provided by OTC, containing the appropriate versions of the required stack: NVIDIA drivers, cuda, Tensorflow 1, etc. The usage of the tool is rather simple, the user only has to configure it by filling a YAML file. More details can be found here: https://gitlab.cern.ch/ipeluaga/engan_etc. Once the VM is ready, the user can ssh to the virtual machine and run the code. The dependencies for the project required was already installed in the virtual machine and hence there wasn't any need for manually installing the libraries. The configuration preset is taken as "preset-v2-4gpus" which is the optimized configuration for 4 GPUs. For the total-king, which refers to the

iterations of training process is set to 6000. The configuration and code for implementation can be found at <https://github.com/surenbthapa/CProGAN-ME-summer-Openlab>. The input can be flexibly changed in the code for different datasets and the training can indeed be carried with multiple datasets.

5. RESULTS

The training was done with 8576 images that took around 2.5 days with the configurations provided above. The trained generator was then used to generate the bottom right tile of 256 X 256 images which were set out for the validation purpose. The 1000 images kept aside from the original 9576 images is the validation data. As mentioned earlier, the 256 X 256 image is sliced into four tiles and the three tiles except the bottom right is used for conditioning purpose. The generator then generates the bottom right image of size 128 X 128. All four 128 X 128 tiles were again arranged back to get the original 256 X 256 images. The main reason for arranging the 128 X 128 tiles back to the original 256 X 256 image is to ensure that the conditioning is indeed happening. If the conditioning is happening, the bottom right tile should reflect the distribution from the previous three tiles on which the generation of the bottom right tile is conditioned. Some of the results can be shown in table 1.

Table 1. Examples of the results by generator

Image Ref. No.	Real images	Fake Images
tile_11_68.png		
tile_12_82.png		
tile_12_44.png		

6. DISCUSSION

The generated images are a bit harder to evaluate for its correctness and usefulness. Thus, we need to assess the quality of the images with some analytical measures. To evaluate how well and useful the generated images were, we used the UNet model developed by Nemni et al [2]. The UNet model is trained on real satellite images to detect water. The classification is binary classification with two classes: water and background. The example in fig. 4 shows that the UNet AI model detects the flood even when the images are synthetically generated. Thus, we come up to a conclusion that the generated GAN image quality is such that UNet model which is trained on real images produces entirely plausible flood maps even with the generated images. A visual inspection of UNet output does not provide evidence of

Figure 4 Output of UNet model on a generated image

differences between the generated dataset and the original one.

7. CONCLUSION

In this experiment, we were able to generate visually plausible synthetic satellite imagery of Myanmar flood dataset using conditional progressive GANs with multiple encoders. The usefulness and the quality of images were assessed on the basis of qualitative analysis using UNet model. The quality of the

generated images can be assessed using more robust quantitative measures like Fréchet Inception Distance (FID), Sliced Wasserstein Distance (SWD), etc. The assessment of the quality can also be done with common datasets like CELEBA, LSUN, CIFAR10, etc. It would unravel even more use cases of CProGAN-ME for applications other than the generation of satellite imagery. Also, the experiment focuses on generation of a single bottom right tile of a larger image. The experiment can be extended to build a larger image tile by tile using a multi-conditioning approach. Such approach helps to generate very correct and spectrally valid images as the CProGAN-ME preserves the key-feature of Conditional GAN to produce an approximation of the full conditional distribution.

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